

5,7-Dimethoxyisochroman-1-one³, colourless needles, m.p. 97-98° (35% yield).

6,7-Methylenedioxyisochroman-1-one¹, colourless prisms, m.p. 126-27° (25% yield).

5-Methoxy-7-methylisochroman-1-one⁴, cubes, m.p. 79-80° (yield 42% yield).

6-Methoxy-7-benzyloxyisochroman-1-one⁵, yellow shining flakes, m.p. 125-26° on trituration with pet. ether (yield 50%) was debenzylated by catalytic hydrogenation over Pd-C and subsequently treated with diazomethane to furnish 6-methoxy-isochroman-1-one, 139-40°.

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Synthesis of 2, 6-Diaryl-5 : 6-Dihydro-4H-1 : 3-Thiazines

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SEVERAL diversely substituted 2, 6-Diaryl-5 : 6-dihydro-4H-1 : 3-thiazines are synthesized using method of Giordano et al^{1,2}, and their structures confirmed by elemental analysis, infra-red spectra and in few cases mass spectra. These (Table 2) were prepared by condensation of N(Hydroxymethyl)-thiobenzamides³ (Table 1) and styrenes in acetic acid.

Experimental

N-Hydroxymethyl Thiobenzamides: These were prepared by heating a mixture of thiobenzamides (0.02 mole), 200 ml. water, 20 ml. 40% formaldehyde (0.5 mole) on a water bath for 15-30 minutes. Contents were cooled and extracted with ether, ether stripped off after drying to get title products (vide Table 1).

2, 6-Diaryl-5 : 6-Dihydro-4H-1 : 3-Thiazines: To a stirred solution of N-Hydroxymethyl-thiobenzamide (0.045 mole) and styrene (0.045 mole) in glacial acetic acid (70 ml) was added conc. sulfuric acid (0.045 mole) dropwise so as to maintain the reaction mixture around 15°. After addition, stirring at this temperature was maintained for six hours and mixture left overnight at room temperature. It was then poured onto crushed ice and basified with 40% aq. sodium hydroxide keeping temp. ~ 10°. The solution was now extracted with ether, ether

TABLE-1

PHENYL-SUBSTITUTED-N-HYDROXYMETHYL-THIOBENZAMIDES

No.	R	M.P. °C.	% age yield	Molecular Formula	%N		%S	
					Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6	7	8	9
1.	H	65 ^a	91	C ₉ H ₉ NOS	—	—	—	—
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	86	88	C ₉ H ₁₁ NOS	7.64	7.73	17.60	17.67
3.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	84	83	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S	6.99	7.10	16.11	16.24
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	90-91 ^b	87	C ₈ H ₈ ClNOS	—	—	—	—
5.	<i>p</i> -Br	69	84	C ₈ H ₈ BrNOS	5.63	5.69	13.00	13.02
6.	3 : 4-Methylenedioxy.	92	78	C ₉ H ₉ NO ₂ S	6.55	6.63	15.15	15.17

^a. Reported by H. Böhme, and H. H. Hotzel, *Arch. Pharm.* 1967, **300**, 241.

^b. Reported by C. Giordano, *Synthesis*, 1972, No. 1, 34-35.

TABLE-2

2, 6-DIARYL-5, 6-DIHYDRO-4H-1, 3-THIAZINES

No.	R	R ₁	M.P./B.P. °C.	HCl M.P., °C.	Molecular Formula	%N		%S	
						Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.	H	H	86-87 ^a	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ NS	—	—	—	—
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	110 ^a	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NS	—	—	—	—
3.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	H	65	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	4.84	4.95	11.22	11.31
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	96 ^a	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClNS	—	—	—	—
5.	<i>p</i> -Br	H	91-92	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ BrNS	4.13	4.22	9.58	9.64
6.	3, 4-Methylenedioxy.	H	107-108	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ NO ₂ S	4.61	4.71	10.69	10.77
7.	-H	-CH ₂	103-105/760 mm.	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NS.HCl	4.54	4.62	10.50	10.56
8.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-CH ₂	242-760 mm	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NS.HCl	4.34	4.41	10.04	10.09
9.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	-CH ₂	239-41/760 mm	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NO ₂ .HCl	4.10	4.21	9.55	9.60
10.	<i>p</i> -Cl	-CH ₂	228/760 mm	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNS.HCl	4.07	4.14	9.41	9.47
11.	<i>p</i> -Br	-CH ₂	236/760 mm	89-90	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrNS.HCl	3.54	3.66	8.31	8.37
12.	3, 4-Methylenedioxy.	-CH ₂	78-80	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	4.38	4.50	10.19	10.29
13.	-H	-OCH ₂	85	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂	4.85	4.95	11.23	11.31
14.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-OCH ₂	230/760 mm	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NO ₂ .HCl	4.11	4.21	9.54	9.60
15.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	-OCH ₂	239-40/760 mm	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NO ₂ .HCl	3.92	4.01	9.09	9.16
16.	<i>p</i> -Cl	-OCH ₂	227/760 mm	76	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNOS.HCl	3.86	3.97	8.99	9.04
17.	<i>p</i> -Br	-OCH ₂	237-38/760 mm	81	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrNOS.HCl	3.40	3.52	7.96	8.04
18.	3, 4-Methylenedioxy.	-OCH ₂	88-89	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	4.16	4.28	9.70	9.79
19.	-H	-Cl	227/760 mm	82-83	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClNS.HCl	4.22	4.33	9.84	9.88
20.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-Cl	230-31/760 mm	93-95	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNS.HCl	4.05	4.14	9.40	9.47
21.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	-Cl	232/760 mm	80-81	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNOS.HCl	3.88	3.97	8.98	9.04
22.	<i>p</i> -Cl	-Cl	213/760 mm	88	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ NS.HCl	3.81	3.91	8.90	8.93
23.	<i>p</i> -Br	-Cl	226/760 mm	82-84	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ BrClNS.HCl	3.39	3.48	7.88	7.94
24.	3, 4-Methylenedioxy.	-Cl	76	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂ S	4.13	4.23	9.59	9.66

^a Reported by C. Giordano, *Synthesis*, 1972, No. 1, 34-35.

solution washed with 2N HCl (2 × 50 ml) at ~ 10° and acid extract made alkaline by 40% aq. alkali. This was extracted with ether and after drying ethereal solution, it gave on evaporation thiazines (vide Table 2). If the product was liquid, it was isolated as hydrochloride. Yields were in the range of 30 to 50%.

I.R. Spectra of all these thiazines show absorption band at 1634-1600 cm⁻¹ typical of C=N linkage present in dihydro-1, 3-thiazines as reported earlier⁴. Mol. Weights of first three were checked by their mass spectra.

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Synthesis of 3-Phenylsulphonamido-4-methoxybenzoic Acid Hydrazide and their Derivatives

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IN continuation of the work done by us on hydrazides and their derivatives as antibacterial agents^{1,2} we extend the work to 3-phenylsulphonamido-4-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide. The hydrazide was synthesised and various N-benzylidene derivatives were prepared by condensing it with aromatic aldehydes. Condensation of the hydrazide with isothiocyanates yielded the thiosemicarbazides which were cyclised to 3,4-disubstituted-5-mercapto-1,2,4-4H triazole³.

Experimental

3-Chlorosulphonylamisic acid was prepared in 64% yield by the chlorosulphonation of anisic acid using 6 moles of chlorosulphonic acid at 65-70^o, m.p. 178^o. (Found : C, 38.44 ; H, 3.0 ; S, 12.58 ;